

Authors	Title	DOI	Link	Abstract	Relevant title?	Relevant abstract?
Dawes S.S., Vidi	Planning and designing open government data programs: An	10.1016/j.giq.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The open government data (OGD) movement has rapidly expanded worl	1	1
Baack S.	Datafication and empowerment: How the open data moveme	10.1177/2053951	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This article shows how activists in the open data movement re-articulate	1	1
Ruijter E., Grimm	Open data for democracy: Developing a theoretical framework	10.1016/j.giq.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data platforms are hoped to foster democratic processes, yet rece	1	1
Ruijter E., Grimm	Connecting societal issues, users and data. Scenario-based	10.1016/j.giq.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Governments around the world make their data available through platfor	1	1
Ruijter E., Meijer	Open Government Data as an Innovation Process: Lessons f	Open Governme	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open government data are claimed to contribute to transparency, citizen	1	1
Alexopoulos C., I	A platform for closing the open data feedback loop based on	10.29379/jedem.	https://www.scopus.com/inw	One essential characteristic of open data ecosystems is their developme	1	1
Ruijter E., Grimm	Open data work: understanding open data usage from a prac	10.1177/0020852	https://www.scopus.com/inw	During recent years, the amount of data released on platforms by public	1	1
Choi J., Tausczik	Characteristics of collaboration in the emerging practice of op	10.1145/2998181	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The democratization of data science and open government data initiative	1	1
Kassen M.	Adopting and managing open data: Stakeholder perspectives	10.1108/AJIM-11	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to study a multi-institutional and m	1	1
Riginos C., Cran	Building a global genomics observatory: Using GEOME (the	10.1111/1755-091	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Genetic data represent a relatively new frontier for our understanding of g	1	1
Beno M., Figl K.,	Perception of key barriers in using and publishing open data	10.29379/jedem.	https://www.scopus.com/inw	There is a growing body of literature recognizing the benefits of Open Da	1	1
Kjærgaard M.B.,	Current practices and infrastructure for open data based rese	10.1016/j.builden	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Many new tools for improving the design and operation of buildings try to	1	1
Mutuku L.N., Col	Increasing kenyan open data consumption: A design thinking	10.1145/2463728	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In July 2011, the Kenyan Government became the twenty-second govern	1	1
Mercado-Lara E.	Open government and data intermediaries: The case of add	10.1145/2612733	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open Government initiatives can improve transparency, participation, and	1	1
Quix C., Chakrat	Business process modelling for a data exchange platform		https://www.scopus.com/inw	The digitization of companies and their business processes is a central c	1	1
Park S., Gil-Garc	Open data innovation: Visualizations and process redesign a	10.1016/j.giq.202	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open government data has led to public policy innovation in pursuit of va	1	1
Begany G.M., M&	An open health data engagement ecosystem model: Are facil	10.1002/pras.202	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Over the last decade, a rapidly growing open data movement has resulte	1	1
Slobodova O., B&	Zooming Into the Ecosystem: Agency and Politics Around Op	10.3389/frsc.202	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data platforms provide free access to datasets in key areas of urba	1	1
Kawashita I., Baç	Open Government Data Use in the Brazilian States and Fede	10.3390/data701	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This research investigates whether, why, and how open government data	1	1
Shehata A., Elgl	Saudi scholars' perceptions and use of open government dat	10.1177/0340035	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This article reports the findings of a study on open data usage among Sa	1	1
Corbett J., Temp	Integrating across sustainability, political, and administrative	10.17705/1CAIS.	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Over the last decade, cities around the world have embraced the open d	1	1
Torino E., Trevis	Semantic enrichment for open data availability: Theory and p	10.5007/1518-29	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Objective: Present the formalization process necessary to make open da	1	1
De Freitas J.L., M	A critical study of electronic participation, transparency and o	10.1504/IJEG.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This study compares two Latin American open government programs by	1	1
Schweiger C.	Open data: Challenges and opportunities for transit agencies		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Within the past five years, more and more transit agencies are making sc	1	1
Kronkosky C.E.,	Improved oil recovery estimation with data analytic methods:	10.2118/185740-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Reserve evaluators use the Secondary to Primary recovery ratio (S:P rat	1	1
Angeles K., Patsi	Advancing resilient and sustainable buildings through a new	10.1061/978078-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Traditionally assessment of building sustainability has focused on operati	1	1
Shi L., Wurm M.,	Estimating housing vacancy rates at block level: The exampl	10.1016/j.landur	https://www.scopus.com/inw	For the real estate market, housing prices as well as housing vacancy rat	1	1
Styrin E., Luna-R	Open data ecosystems: an international comparison	10.1108/TG-01-2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: In this paper, the authors compare the open government data (1	
Gértrudix M., Ge	Consumption of public institutions' opendata by Spanish citiz	10.3145/epi.2016	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The consumption practices of Spanish citizens of open data published by	1	
Vicente-Saez R.,	The dawn of an open exploration era: Emergent principles ar	10.1016/j.techfor	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Principles and practices of open science at universities are evolving. Incr	1	
Johansson D., L&	Mobile e-Services and Open Data in e-Government processe	10.1145/2837185	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Mobile computing is one of the most important paradigms to inuence and	1	
Zheng L., Gao F.	Assessment on China's open government data platforms: Fra	10.1145/2912160	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The research establishes an assessment framework on government ope	1	
Bacon S., Golda	Barriers to working with national health service England's ope	10.2196/15603	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data is information made freely available to third parties in structu	1	
Hunnius S., Krieç	The social shaping of open data through administrative proce	10.1145/2641580	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Many models have been provided in the last years that aim at describing	1	
Kitsios F., Kamar	Digital Entrepreneurship Services Evolution: Analysis of Quac	10.3390/su13211	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data hackathons are events where the actors from an ecosystem c	1	
Hodonu-Wusu J.	Malaysian researchers on open data: The first national surve	10.22452/mjliis.v	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The study investigates the awareness, practices and attitudes of researc	1	
Abdullahi K.A., N	Perceptions towards research data sharing: A qualitative stud	10.22452/mjliis.v	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open science provides transparency to research processes by means of	1	
Herala A., Kasuri	Current status and the future directions of open data: Percep	10.1145/2994310	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data has been a hot topic of the decade, as even the president of t	1	

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Ponciano J.-J., P	From acquisition to presentation—the potential of semantics	10.3390/rs13112	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The signature of the 2019 Declaration of Cooperation on advancing the c	1	
Yang T.-M., Wu M	An exploration of factors influencing Taiwan government age	10.1145/3396956	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data is a complex process and its ecosystem includes various stak	1	
Ramadhan G., K	A study on the guideline to implement open data activities based on the risk ma		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data is a kind of data that can be used independently as well as us	1	
Clarke A., Marge	Governments and citizens getting to know each other? open,	10.1002/1944-28	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Citizens and governments live increasingly digital lives, leaving trails of d	1	
Susha I., Zuiderv	Benchmarks for Evaluating the Progress of Open Data Adopt	10.1177/0894439	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Public organizations release their data for use by the public to open the g	1	
Sicilia M.-A., Vis	Blockchain and OECD data repositories: opportunities and pr	10.1108/LHT-12-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to employ the case of Organizatio	1	
Alanazi J.M., Ch	Sharing government-owned data with the public: A cross-country analysis of o		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Since 2009, open government policies, open data, and social media use	1	
Casalino N., Buo	Transparency, openness and knowledge sharing for rebuildin	10.2316/P.2013.7	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The developing of the Open Government Model is allowing an organizati	1	
Serra L.E.C.	The mapping, selecting and opening of data: The records ma	10.1108/RMJ-01-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose – This paper aims to share the contribution of records managers	1	
Masip-Bruin X., F	Unlocking the value of open data with a process-based inform	10.1109/CBI.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	There has been a wide shift in the way data are managed in the public ad	1	
Estermann B.	Diffusion of open data and crowdsourcing among heritage ins	10.4067/S0718-1	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In a pilot survey we examined the diffusion of open data and crowdsourc	1	
Maccani G., Don	Exploring the factors that influence the diffusion of open data for new service d		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Information Systems research on Open Data has been primarily focused	1	
Hoxha J., Brahaj	Open.data.al: Increasing the utilization of government data in	10.1145/2063518	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open Data practice requires that data are freely available for everyone, k	1	
Stone M., Aravop	Improving journeys by opening data: the case of Transport fo	10.1108/BL-12-21	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: This case study describes how one of the world's largest public	1	
Zubcoff J.J., Vaq	The university as an open data ecosystem	10.2495/DNE-V1	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Lately, the University of Alicante (Spain) started the OpenData4U project	1	
Vracic T., Varga M	Effects and evaluation of open government data initiative in C	10.1109/MIPRO.:	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The paper is a follow-up to a previous paper where the authors describ	1	
Kansa S.W.	Using linked open data to improve data aruse in zooarchaeol	10.14237/ebl.6.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The inability of journals and books to accommodate data and to make it a	1	
Rüping S.	Big data in medicine and healthcare [Big Data in Medizin und	10.1007/s00103-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Healthcare is one of the business fields with the highest Big Data potenti	1	
Maccani G., Don	Open Data diffusion for service innovation: An inductive case study on cultural		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Information Systems research on Open Data has been primarily focused	1	
Zuiderwijk A., Jar	Workshop: Linking open data: Challenges and solutions	10.1145/2307729	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data have been recognized as a way to advance citizen engageme	1	
Machado V., Mar	An instrument for evaluating open data portals: A case study	10.1145/3209281	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data portals are fundamental tools for governments to achieve pub	1	
Towse J.N., Ellis	Opening Pandora's Box: Peeking inside Psychology's data st	10.3758/s13428-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data-sharing is a valuable practice that ought to enhance the impac	1	
Corrales-Garay L	A Research Agenda on Open Data Impact Process for Open	10.1109/ACCES:	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data and open innovation are two topics currently attracting the att	1	
Fox R., Bourn N.	Opinions of citizen scientists on open access to UK butterfly c	10.1007/s10531-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Citizen science plays an increasingly important role in biodiversity resear	1	
Saddiqa M., Ras	Bringing open data into Danish schools and its potential impa	10.1145/3306446	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Private and public institutions are using open and public data to provide t	1	
García Rodríguez	Spanish Public Procurement: Legislation, open data source a	10.1016/j.procs.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open Data in Public Administrations and, in particular, the publications of	1	
Gasco-Hernande	The role of management in open data initiatives in local gove	10.29379/jedem.	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Previous studies have infrequently addressed the dynamic interactions a	1	
Han M.-J.K.	Establishing sustainable and scalable workflows for catalogin	10.1108/LM-04-2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: Academic and research libraries have been experiencing a lot o	1	
Berro A., Megdic	Graph-based ETL processes for Warehousing Statistical Ope	10.5220/000536:	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Warehousing is a promising mean to cross and analyse Statistical Open	1	
Drakopoulou S.	Open data today and tomorrow: The present challenges and	10.1504/IJEG.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper argues that because of the present challenges of open data, e	1	
Chunpir H.I., Zair	Assisting users in open data infrastructures: A management perspective		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Utilizing user support is an essential activity in e-Science to maintain and	1	
Cook B.G., Lloyd	Open science in the field of emotional and behavioral disorde	10.1353/etc.2019	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Students with emotional and behavioral disorders (EBD) present some o	1	
Cabitzza F., Del Z	Probing interactivity in open data for General Practice. An evidence-based app		https://www.scopus.com/inw	We undertook a user study to evaluate whether the perceived utility of so	1	
Villa D.	Crowdsourced Heritage Tourism Open-Data, Small-Data and	10.1007/978-3-3	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Many new questions arise with regard to Web3.0-based technologies, m	1	
Arman A.A., Rarr	Design of data management guideline for open data impleme	10.1145/2846012	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data is the idea that some data should be freely available to everyo	1	
Cooper C.B., Ra	Perspective: The Power (Dynamics) of Open Data in Citizen	10.3389/fclim.20:	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In citizen science, data stewards and data producers are often not the sa	1	
Caballero-Rivero	Open science practices of the Brazilian academic community	10.1590/2318-08	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open Science represents a new approach to scientific work, resulting fro	1	
Zeleti F.A., Ojo A	Agile mechanisms for open data process innovation in public	10.1145/3326365	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Process innovation in public organizations is widely documented and has	1	

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Rosim S., De Fre	Open data practices: The case of South America drainage da	10.1109/CHILEC	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Fruit of a collaboration between two international research institutions, th	1	
Payne P.R.O., Hu	Open data for discovery science	10.1142/9789813	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The modern healthcare and life sciences ecosystem is moving towards a	1	
Cleland B., Galbr	Configuration processes in open data	10.1109/ICE.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data is an emerging challenge for public sector managers, and rep	1	
Mandeville C.P.,	Open Data Practices among Users of Primary Biodiversity Da	10.1093/biosci/bi	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Presence-only biodiversity data are increasingly relied on in biodiversity,	1	
Baždarić K., Vrki	Attitudes and practices of open data, preprinting, and peer-re	10.1371/journal.g	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Attitudes towards open peer review, open data and use of preprints influe	1	
Izdebski W., Zwi	Open data in spatial data infrastructure: the practices and ex	10.1080/1753894	https://www.scopus.com/inw	As an important facilitator in e-government and society in general, Open	1	
Kaußen L., Witt	Practical suitability of publicly available geodata in Germany	10.17433/11.202	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The European INSPIRE Directive harmonises the provision of free geoda	1	
Ante M.A., Ante	Towards information transparency: Current posture and advo	10.2118/198795-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Transparency in information is one of the most important undertaking tha	1	
Lobos V.E., Dian	Proposal of a unified BPM model for open data publication	10.1109/ICEDEG	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The Open Government paradigm uses open data as a tool to generate tr	1	
Heuss T., Fengel	A field study on linked and open data at Datahub.io		https://www.scopus.com/inw	We describe and conduct a study on datahub.io to explore to what, in pra	1	
Jäger B., Bartent	Open data: Challenges and future directions		https://www.scopus.com/inw	The rapid expansion of Open Data enforces the distribution and availabil	1	
Previtali M., Vale	Archaeological documentation and data sharing: Digital surve	10.4995/var.2019	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The open data paradigm is changing the research approach in many field	1	
Zuiderwijk A., Jar	Design principles for improving the process of publishing ope	10.1108/TG-07-2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to derive design principles for impr		
Ruijter E.H.J.M., I	Researching the democratic impact of open government data	10.3233/IP-1704	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This systematic literature review examines the impact of open governme		
Martin E.G., Helt	Opening health data: What do researchers want? Early experi	10.1097/PHH.00	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Context: Governments are rapidly developing open data platforms to imp		
Kubler S., Rober	Open data portal quality comparison using AHP	10.1145/2912160	https://www.scopus.com/inw	During recent years, more and more Open Data becomes available and i		
Kučera J., Chlap	Methodologies and best practices for Open Data publication		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Publication and reuse of machine-readable data on the Web is one of the		
Roth J., Lim B., J	Examining the feasibility of using open data to benchmark bu	10.1016/j.enpol.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Buildings are by far the largest source of urban energy consumption. In a		
Bartenberger M.,	The enabling effects of open government data on collaborati	10.29379/jedem.	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The term “smart city” has been strongly promoted since the late 1990s, y		
Parraguez P., Ma	Data-driven engineering design research: Opportunities using open data		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Engineering Design research relies on quantitative and qualitative data to		
Ben Amer S., Gre	Too complicated and impractical? An exploratory study on the	10.1016/j.erss.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Energy system models can contribute to the transition to low-carbon ene		
Solar M., Daniels	A model to guide the open government data implementation in public agencies		https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper presents a model to diagnose maturity and capabilities of Pub		
Gold E.R., Ali-Kh	An open toolkit for tracking open science partnership implem	10.12688/gateso	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Serious concerns about the way research is organized collectively are in		
Klímek J.	DCAT-AP representation of Czech National Open Data Catal	10.1016/j.webser	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data is now a heavily discussed topic around the world and in the E		
Safhi H.M., Frikh	Assessing reliability of Big Data Knowledge Discovery proces	10.1016/j.procs.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Extracting knowledge from Big Data is the process of transforming this d		
Zeleti F.A., Ojo	Competitive capability framework for open government data	10.1145/3085228	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data-driven organizations compete in a complex and uncertain env		
Alfano M., Lenzit	A framework for opening data and creating advanced service	10.1145/2983468	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data is publicly available data that can be universally and readily a		
Folmer E., Beek	Enhancing the usefulness of open governmental data with linked data viewing		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open Governmental Data publishing has had mixed success. While man		
Asano Y., Koide	Constructing a Site for Publishing Open Data of the Ministry	10.1007/s00354-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	We describe a procedure for constructing a website for publishing open c		
von Blumesberge	The world of metadata in the universe of repositories [Die we	10.31263/voebm	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Within the scope of the Austria-wide project „eInfrastructures Austria“, in		
Lee M.-H.	Challenges of designing with open data: The case of cultural	10.15187/adr.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Background While the promise of a data-driven economy lies to a large e		
Spiegelman E.	Esteemed Colleagues: A Model of the Effect of Open Data or	10.3389/fpsyg.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data, the practice of making available to the research community th		
Mao W.-H., Jan	Visualization of open data: A case study of climate data		https://www.scopus.com/inw	The development of technology has promoted large amount of data to tra		
Estermann B.	Are memory institutions ready for open data and crowdsourci	10.1145/2491058	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Since the advent of the World Wide Web, the cultural heritage sector has		
Anseeuw W., Lay	Creating a public tool to assess and promote transparency in	10.1080/0306618	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The Beta version of the Land Matrix (Land Matrix 2012) was launched in		
Kubler S., Rober	Comparison of metadata quality in open data portals using th	10.1016/j.giq.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The quality of metadata in open data portals plays a crucial role for the st		
Hinkson I.V., Dav	A comprehensive infrastructure for big data in cancer researc	10.3389/fcell.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Advancements in next-generation sequencing and other -omics technolo		
Arheimer B., Pim	Global catchment modelling using World-Wide HYPE (WWH)	10.5194/hess-24	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Recent advancements in catchment hydrology (such as understanding c		

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Borglund E., Eng	Open data? Data, information, document or record?	10.1108/RMJ-01-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose – The aim of the article is to investigate what characterizes the i		
Attila M., Michel	Reframing open big data		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Recent developments in the techniques and technologies of collecting, sl		
Vega-Gorgojo G. Pepe	Search: Semantic Data for the masses	10.1371/journal.g	https://www.scopus.com/inw	With the emergence of the Web of Data, there is a need of tools for sear		
Piedra N., Chicai	A rating system that open-data repositories must satisfy to be	10.1109/EDUCO	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The re-use of digital content is an essential part of the knowledge-based		
Sharif B., Lundin	Developing a digital data collection platform to measure the p	10.1093/jamia/oc	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Objective To develop a secure, efficient, and easy-to-use data collection		
Fleming J.I., Wils	Open accessibility in education research: Enhancing the cred	10.1080/0046152	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Openness is a foundational principle in science. Making the tools and pro		
Coughlan T.	The use of open data as a material for learning	10.1007/s11423-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data has potential value as a material for use in learning activities.		
Meng A.	Investigating the roots of open data's social impact	10.29379/jedem.	https://www.scopus.com/inw	It is a challenging and urgent task to innovate democracy. Open governm		
Liu T., Bouali F.,	EXOD: A tool for building and exploring a large graph of oper	10.1016/j.cag.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	We present in this paper a tool called EXOD (EXploration of Open Datas		
Omri A., Benouai	Querying Data Services in an Uncertain Environment: A Poss	10.1109/SITIS.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The acceptance of open data practices by individuals and organizations l		
Krumova M.	Higher education 2.0 and open data: A framework for univers	10.1145/3047273	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This research addresses the key role of web 2.0 tools in Higher Educatio		
Hagedorn S., Sai	Discovery querying in linked open data	10.1145/2457317	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The problem of the inability of machines to interpret and process informa		
Rubin A.	What to consider when we consider data	10.1111/test.1227	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The data sets used in statistics education have changed over time, from		
Rautenberg S., M	Linked open data and knowledge management: Scientometri	10.1590/1981-53	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper is based on the relation of three concepts: Knowledge Manag		
Jane H.-B., Faily	Applying contextual integrity to open data publishing	10.14236/ewic/H	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data publishing by both corporate and public bodies has increased		
Reilly K.M.A., Alç	Intermediation in open development: A knowledge stewardship approach		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open Development (OD) is a subset of ICT4D that studies the potential c		
Ostendorff M., Bl	Towards an open platform for legal information	10.1145/3383583	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Recent advances in the area of legal information systems have led to a v		
Zeng M.L., Cluni	FAIR + FIT: Guiding Principles and Functional Metrics for Lin	10.2478/jdis-202	https://www.scopus.com/inw	To develop a set of metrics and identify criteria for assessing the function		
Singer D., Borrm	A novel knowledge-based engineering approach for infrastructure design		https://www.scopus.com/inw	In this paper, a novel knowledge-based engineering (KBE) approach for t		
Wallezky L., Ror	Research challenges of open data as a service for smart cities		https://www.scopus.com/inw	The open data are considered to be an important building block of Smart		
MacHado J.S., F	Towards open data in digital education platforms	10.1109/ICALT.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Despite the traction gained by the open data movement and the rise of bi		
Verma N., Gupta	Challenges in publishing open government data: A study in Ir	10.1145/2846012	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Governments across the world are striving to bring more and more transp		
Quemy A., Wrem	ECHR-OD: On building an integrated open repository of lega	10.1016/j.is.2021	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper presents an exhaustive and unified repository of judgments d		
Visintin L., Tode	Open data maturity model: A reference matrix for organizations [MODELO DE		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data is a widespread topic due to the benefits that can be observec		
Li S., Chen Y.	Explaining the resistance of data providers to open governme	10.1108/AJIM-09	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: This paper explains the formation of government resistance to c		
Ma C.-C., Yang T	Exploring Government Officials' Data Collection Process in O	10.6120/JoEMLS	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The implementation of open government data (OGD) initiatives has beco		
Norlander B., We	Open data publishing by public libraries	10.1109/JCDL.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Public libraries in the USA are part of a broad civic information ecosyste		
Greene G., Plant	Building open access to research (OAR) data infrastructure a	10.5334/dsj-2019	https://www.scopus.com/inw	As a National Metrology Institute (NMI), the USA National Institute of Sta		
Nilsson E.M., Wi	Urban Archiving for Smarter Cities: Archival Practices beyonc	10.1109/Culture.:	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Urban Archiving is a research theme within the project Living Archives ex		
Pereira L.M.F., M	OGDPub: Domain ontology for open data publishing by Brazilian municipalities		https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper reports the development of a domain ontology for open data p		
Sanderson S.C.,	Public Attitudes toward Consent and Data Sharing in Biobank	10.1016/j.ajhg.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Individuals participating in biobanks and other large research projects are		
Schür C., Rist S.	When Fluorescence Is not a Particle: The Tissue Translocati	10.1002/etc.4436	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Abstract: Previous research reported the translocation of nano- and micr		
Ridgway J.	Implications of the Data Revolution for Statistics Education	10.1111/insr.1211	https://www.scopus.com/inw	There has never been a more exciting time to be involved in statistics. Er		
Li Y., Guan K., Yu	Toward building a transparent statistical model for improving	10.1016/j.fcr.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Statistical crop models have been a major tool in identifying critical driver		
Komninos N., Ka	Smart City Planning from an Evolutionary Perspective	10.1080/1063073	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In the theory of urban development, the evolutionary perspective is beco		
Hiver P., Al-Hoori	Reexamining the Role of Vision in Second Language Motivat	10.1111/lang.123	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Researchers have linked vivid mental imagery, particularly of the self in fi		
Zarate O.A., Bro	Balancing Benefits and Risks of Immortal Data: Participants'	10.1002/hast.523	https://www.scopus.com/inw	An individual's health, genetic, or environmental-exposure data, placed ir		
Ruijter E., Déti	The Politics of Open Government Data: Understanding Organi	10.1177/0275074	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This article contributes to the growing body of literature within public man		

Authors	Title	DOI	Link	Abstract	Relevant title?	Relevant abstract?
Davies T., Edward	Emerging implications of open and linked data for knowledge	10.1111/j.1759-5424.2015.00541.x	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Movements towards open data involve the publication of datasets (from r		
McDonald J., Lévesque	Whither the retention schedule in the era of big data and open	10.1108/RMJ-01-2014-0001	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose – This article, which is one of the products of an international co		
Witek D., Grettarsson	Teaching metaliteracy: A new paradigm in action	10.1108/RSR-07-2014-0001	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to offer a model of information lite		
Jetzek T., Avital M	The sustainable value of open government data	10.17705/1jais.0001	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Building on the promise of open data, government agencies support a co		
Albert S., de Ruit	Repair: The Interface Between Interaction and Cognition	10.1111/tops.12301	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Conversational repair is the process people use to detect and resolve pr		
Gradmann S.	From containers to content to context: The changing role of li	10.1108/JD-05-2014-0001	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: The aim of this paper is to reposition the research library in the		
Nicholas D., Jamnik	A global questionnaire survey of the scholarly communication	10.1002/leap.128	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This article describes an international study informed by a 3-year-long qu		
Gorriani A., Bertini	Walkability assessment and tourism cities: the case of Venice	10.1108/IJTC-11-2014-0001	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to propose a systematic review of f		
Consoli S., Presu	An urban fault reporting and management platform for smart	10.1145/2740908	https://www.scopus.com/inw	A good interaction between public administrations and citizens is imperat		
Immonen A., Ova	Towards certified open data in digital service ecosystems	10.1007/s11219-015-0001-0	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The opportunities of open data have been recently recognized among co		
Huang B., Di Y., et al.	Review of data-driven prognostics and health management techniques: Lessio	10.1108/JD-05-2014-0001	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Machine learning and statistical algorithms are receiving considerable att		
Beisken S., Earle	MassCascade: Visual programming for LC-MS data processi	10.1002/minf.2014.0001	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS) is comm		
Joel S., Eastwick	Open Sharing of Data on Close Relationships and Other Sen	10.1177/2515245141680001	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This article reports on an adversarial (but friendly) collaboration examin		
Schallow J., Lud	Future prospects for digital manufacturing Understanding, realization status an	10.1108/JD-05-2014-0001	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Within an extensive survey carried out by the Institute of Production Syst		
Cummings J.A., et al.	Impact of open data policies on consent to participate in hum	10.1371/journal.p	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Research outlets are increasingly adopting open data policies as a requi		
Jormanainen I., S	Using data mining to support teacher's intervention in a robot	10.1109/DIGITEL	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Following students' progress in robotics classes is difficult because stude		
Sun Z., Majaneva	DNA metabarcoding adds valuable information for managem	10.1002/ece3.55	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Abstract: Stormwater ponds are used to compensate for the adverse effe		
Johnson I.G., Pu	Neighbourhood data: Exploring the role of open data in local	10.1145/3274352	https://www.scopus.com/inw	There is a growing public, political, and academic discourse around the ic		
Lucas L., Boumg	Machine learning for spacecraft operations support - the mar	10.1109/SMC-IT	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Mars Express (MEX) has been orbiting Mars, generating great science fc		
Assaf A., Senart	Towards an objective assessment framework for linked data	10.4018/IJSWIS	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Ensuring data quality in Linked Open Data is a complex process as it cor		
Berendt B., Hollir	USEWOD2011 - 1st international workshop on usage analysi	10.1145/1963192	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The USEWOD2011 workshop investigates combinations of usage data w		
Cheng D., Cushii	Safety and Efficacy of Tumor Necrosis Factor Antagonists in	10.1016/j.cgh.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Background & Aims: Treatment of older patients (more than 60 years) wit		
An J., Cheng J.,	A Lightweight Blockchain-Based Model for Data Quality Asse	10.1109/TCSS.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	By allocating tasks to participants, crowdsensing has shown large potent		
Hoshi T., Imanish	Density dependence in a seasonal time series of the bamboc	10.4039/tce.2016	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The bamboo mosquito, <i>Tripteroides bambusa</i> (Yamada) (Diptera: Culicid		
Schweitzer L.A.,	09 F9 11 02 9D 74 E3 5B D8 41 56 C5 63 56 88 C0: Four Re	10.1080/0194436	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Problem, research strategy, and findings: Computing and digital technolo		
Ristoski P., Paul	A comparison of propositionalization strategies for creating features from linke	10.1109/ICDM	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Linked Open Data has been recognized as a valuable source for backgr		
Stinson A.D., Fau	Stepping beyond libraries: The changing orientation in global	10.4403/jlis.it-12	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Wikipedia and its community has seen an increasingly close relationship		
Vega-Gorgojo G.	Visual query interfaces for semantic datasets: An evaluation	10.1016/j.webse	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The rapid growth of the Linked Open Data cloud, as well as the increas		
Ayele W., Juell-S	Evaluating open data innovation: A measurement model for digital innovation c	10.1109/IC	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Digital innovation contests emerge as important intermediaries in open d		
Tse K., Hammon	The impact of postsynaptic density 95 blocking peptide (Tat-N	10.1002/jnr.2444	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Abstract: Antiepileptogenic agents that prevent the development of epilep		
Cruz S.M.S.D., N	Towards integration of data-driven agronomic experiments wi	10.1016/j.compa	https://www.scopus.com/inw	With improvements in computing and communications, the amount of sci		
Miao Z., Xiao Y.,	Integration of Satellite Images and Open Data for Impervious	10.1109/JSTARS	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Supervised learning is vital to classify impervious surface from satellite in		
Lewis D., Moorke	Integrating the Management of Personal Data Protection and Open Science wi	10.1109/IC	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper examines the impact of the EU General Data Protection Regu		
Abid T., Laouar M	Smart cities based on web semantic technologies	10.1145/2968219	https://www.scopus.com/inw	A good communication and interaction between citizens and the administ		
Teyhen D.S., Ald	Leveraging technology: Creating and sustaining changes for	10.1089/tmj.2013	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Objective: The rapid growth and evolution of health-related technology ca		
Smith A., Heath	Police.Uk and data.police.uk: Developing open crime and jus	10.29379/jedem	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In this paper we describe the evolution and development of the police.uk		
Vanek N.	Changing Event Categorization in Second Language Users T	10.1111/lang.123	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This study examined the impact of a second language (L2) on how event		
Manning M., Wor	Towards a 'smart' cost-benefit tool: using machine learning t	10.1186/s40163-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Background: The Manning Cost-Benefit Tool (MCBT) was developed to		

Authors	Title	DOI	Link	Abstract	Relevant title?	Relevant abstract?
Koelle R.	Open source software and crowd sourced data for operational performance an		https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper explores the feasibility of using open data and an open source		
Michel F., Gargor	A model to represent nomenclatural and taxonomic information as linked data.		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Taxonomic registers are key tools to help us comprehend the diversity of		
Pu X., Chan F.T.S	Development of a unified Open E-Logistics Standards diffusion model for man		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open E-Logistics Standards (OELS) is important to facilitate the integrati		
Zulkarnain P.D.	IntOGo: Inter-government open government model	10.1109/ICTSS.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Nowadays, most e-government development are moving toward the conc		
Picasso V., Phela	The evolution of open access to research and data in Austral	10.7238/rusc.v11	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open access (OA) in the Australian tertiary education sector is evolving r		
Kourtali N.-E., Re	The Roles of Recasts, Task Complexity, and Aptitude in Child	10.1111/lang.123	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This study investigated the effects of task complexity on child learners' se		
Steinhardt I.	Learning Open Science by doing Open Science. A reflection	10.3233/EFI-190	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Openness in science and education is increasing in importance within the		
Cucarián J.D., Be	Physical exercise and human adipose-derived mesenchymal	10.1002/jnr.2444	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Parkinson's disease (PD) is a disabling and highly costly neurodegenerat		
Pantano E., Prip	Facilitating tourists' decision making through open data analy	10.1016/j.tmp.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	A number of studies have recently been published reporting researchers'		
Letourneau S., E	The effects of neighbourhood characteristics on crime incid	10.1109/CCWC.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Using data from the City of Edmonton, Canada Open Data Portal, an exp		
Tambouris E.	Multidimensional open government data	10.29379/jedem.	https://www.scopus.com/inw	A large amount of open government data concerns official and unofficial :		
Fukuda Y., Oka M	Air traffic open data and its improvement		https://www.scopus.com/inw	To enable wider participation in research to support "Collaborative Action		
Vafopoulos M., M	Insights in global public spending	10.1145/2506182	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Governments around the globe are opening up public spending data in o		
Cifuentes-Silva F	National budget as linked open data: New tools for supportin	10.3390/su12114	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper presents the visualization of national budget, a tool based on		
Kelbert A.	EMTF XML: New data interchange format and conversion too	10.1190/geo2018	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Initial processing of magnetotelluric (MT) data collected at a site results in		
Campus S.F., Sc	The open data kit suite, mobile data collection technology as	10.12899/asr-18	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper examines the potential for using Mobile Data Collection (MDC		
Yang M., Brumar	"Heritage & development" strategy on historic urban landscap	10.5194/isprs-Ar	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Growing interest in boosting urban identity and character is increasing th		
Passarotti M.C.,	The LILA knowledge base of linguistic resources and NLP tools for latin		https://www.scopus.com/inw	The LiLa: Linking Latin project was recently awarded funding from the Eu		
Raffaghelli J.E.,	Is there a social life in open data? The case of open data pra	10.3390/publicati	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In the landscape of Open Science, Open Data (OD) plays a crucial role a		
Tenenbaum J.D.,	Best practices and lessons learned from reuse of 4 patient-d	10.1142/9789813	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The importance of open data has been increasingly recognized in recent		
Medir Tejado L.,	Modelling local autonomy and dependence through cooperat	10.1108/IJPSM-C	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Purpose: Given the spread of multi-level governance tools, interaction be		
Valori L., Gianni	A generation-attraction model for renewable energy flows in I	10.1140/epjst/e2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In recent years, in Italy, the trend of the electricity demand and the need i		
Stephan E.G., El	Semantic catalog of things, services, and data to support a w	10.1007/s10796-	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Transparency and data integrity are crucial to any scientific study wantin		
Chicaiza J., Pied	A contribution to encourage the dissemination of academic p	10.1109/EDUCO	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Scientific production reflects the advances of an academic or research ac		
Schwendicke F.,	Data Dentistry: How Data Are Changing Clinical Care and Re	10.1177/0022034	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Data are a key resource for modern societies and expected to improve q		
Teshome A., Gu	Intimate partner violence among prenatal care attendees ami	10.1002/ijgo.135	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Objective: To assess the incidence and predictors of intimate partner viol		
Tran B.-H., Ausse	An Approach for Integrating Earth Observation, Change Dete	10.1109/IGARSS	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper presents an integration process of open data and Earth Obse		
Degbelo A., Sarfi	Data scale as cartography: a semi-automatic approach for th	10.1080/1523040	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open government promises increased transparency by providing its citizi		
Thindwa D., Farc	Electronic data capture for large scale typhoid surveillance, h	10.12688/wellcor	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Electronic data capture systems (EDCs) have the potential to achieve eff		
Khan M.U., Garc	Service-Based Network Dimensioning for 5G Networks Assis	10.1109/ACCES	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The fifth-generation (5G) of cellular communications is expected to be de		
Peksa J.	Autonomous Open Data Prediction Framework	10.1109/AIEEE4	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The article looks at Open Data and explains the nature of data and how		
Jackson B.	The Changing Research Data Landscape and the Experienc	10.1016/j.acalib.	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Academic libraries have to a large extent taken the lead in facilitating nev		
Azevedo B.M., O	Information visualization: Conceptualizing new paths for filter	10.1109/EPCGI.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	More than 6, 849.32 new research journal articles are published every da		
Maksimenkova C	On practice of using open data in construction of training and	10.1109/ICCSE.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper describes the experience of using open datasets in "Program		
Colmenar E., Mu	Open data offers open opportunities: A case study on improvi	10.1109/IHTC.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Recently, governments have provided citizens data as a resource for pub		
Parker J.	A new scholarship of classroom-based, open, communal inq	10.20343/teachle	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This article argues that SoTL may draw on and inform other scholarships		
Burkhardt D., Sta	Interactive exploration system: A user-centered interaction ap	10.1109/CW.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Nowadays a wide range of input devices are available to users of technic		
Hoces De La Gu	A framework for open policy analysis	10.1093/scipol/sc	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The evidence-based policy movement promotes the use of empirical evic		

Authors	Title	DOI	Link	Abstract	Relevant title?	Relevant abstract?
Dorne J., Aussen	From EO change rasters to knowledge graphs: An approach based on regions		https://www.scopus.com/inw	This paper proposes a process that supports the full life-cycle to generat		
Deitz S., Lobben	Squeaky wheels: Missing data, disability, and power in the sr	10.1177/2053951	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Data about the accessibility of United States municipalities is infrastru		
Boyd M.J., Camp	Open Area, Open Data: Advances in Reflexive Archaeologica	10.1080/0093469	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This article presents a holistic and reflexive process for archaeological fie		
Stein T.	Investigation of the efficiency of work processes within a farm	10.15150/lt.2020	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Research has long been concerned with the investigation and optimizati		
Jegede A., Ajayi	Ethical issues in the COVID-19 pandemic control preparedne	10.11604/pamj.s	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Adequate preparation for highly pathogenic infectious disease pandemic		
Schelstraete J., V	Towards a Sustainable and Collaborative Data Model for Peri	10.1080/1368880	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This article advocates the development of a sustainable, structured, and		
Ahmed J., Ghara	Demo Abstract: A tool to detect and visualize malicious DNS queries for enterp		https://www.scopus.com/inw	This demo presents our web-tool to access and visualize real-time detec		
Ohnishi N., Osav	Landscape heterogeneity in landform and land use provides	10.1002/ece3.51	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Context: Genetic diversity is one of the most important facets of biologica		
Moussallem D., S	Lidioms: A multilingual linked idioms data set		https://www.scopus.com/inw	In this paper, we describe the LIDIOMS data set, a multilingual RDF repr		
Sutjarittham T., H	Demo Abstract: A Tool to Access and Visualize Classroom Att	10.1109/IPSN.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This demo presents our web-tool to access and visualize student attende		
Ahmed H.H.	Data quality assessment in the integration process of linked c	10.1109/AICCSA	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Linked Open Data (LOD) entails a set of best practices for publishing and		
Macharia P., San	Using open data kit in a cluster randomized clinical trial: The assisted partner s		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Paper-based data collection tools are error prone, require more storage s		
Herala A., Kasuri	Views on open data business from software development cor	10.4067/S0718-1	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The interest towards the concept of open data has increased during the I		
Rigaux P., Thion	Quality awareness over graph pattern queries	10.1145/3105831	https://www.scopus.com/inw	We examine the problem of quality awareness when querying graph data		
Duro N., Martins	Collaborative and flexible processing infrastructure for coasta	10.1109/EXPAT.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Coastline Watch aims to assess the best practices to continuously monit		
Hadi A.S.	Distributed genetic algorithm for information retrieval in linke	10.3923/rjasci.20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Information retrieval play an important role in the web. Many research pr		
Rajshree N., Des	A computational model for corruption assessment	10.1145/2516911	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Corruption afflicts public services world-wide and is universally considere		
Minervini P., Fani	Rank prediction for semantically annotated resources	10.1145/2480362	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In the context of semantic knowledge bases, we tackle the problem of ran		
Kolyshkina I., Bro	Improving every child's chance in life	10.1109/ICDMW.	https://www.scopus.com/inw	This article describes the results of a data mining project designed to exp		
Schieferdecker I.	(Open) data quality	10.1109/COMPS	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Be it environmental data, public utility data, geo data, or some other data		
Sadilek C., Simo	Service orchestration for linking open data: Applying a SOA principle to the wel		https://www.scopus.com/inw	The rising popularity of RESTful Web services has recently motivated the		
Thirumuruganath	Automated Annotations for AI Data and Model Transparency	10.1145/3460000	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The data and Artificial Intelligence revolution has had a massive impact o		
Kahn E., Antogn	The LCA Commons—How an Open-Source Repository for U	10.3390/app1202	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a flexible and powerful tool for quantifying		
Pak W., Kim I., C	Proposal of the energy consumption analysis process for the	10.1093/jcde/qw	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Recently, nations around the world have been implementing various polic		
Jares A., Klimek	Simplod: Simple SPARQL Query Builder for Rapid Export of I	10.1145/3487664	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In the last decade, linked open data (LOD) became the de-facto highest s		
Surucu M., Isler	Convolutional neural networks predict the onset of paroxysm	10.1063/5.00692	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In this study, we aimed to detect paroxysmal atrial fibrillation episodes be		
Vinnakota B.	The Open Domain-Specific Architecture: Next Steps to Produ	10.1145/3477206	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Domain-specific architectures (DSAs) are expected to play an increasing		
Bello I.M., Sylves	Real-time monitoring of a circulating vaccine-derived poliovir	10.11604/pamj.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Introduction: the use of digital health technologies and geographical infor		
Austin T., Bei K.,	Lessons learnt from engineering science projects participatin	10.3390/data609	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Trends in the sciences are indicative of data management becoming esta		
Quinn S.	USING FREE and OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE to TEACH U	10.5194/isprs-arc	https://www.scopus.com/inw	During the remote learning necessitated by the COVID-19 pandemic, uni		
Beauvais M.J.S., A	marathon, not a sprint – neuroimaging, Open Science and	10.1016/j.neuroir	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open Science is calling for a radical re-thinking of existing scientific pract		
Lane B., Garousi	An open web-based module developed to advance data-drive	10.1002/hyp.142	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The era of 'big data' promises to provide new hydrologic insights, and op		
Warne R.T., Golig	Factor structure of intelligence and divergent thinking substest	10.1371/journal.p	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Psychologists have investigated creativity for 70 years, and it is now see		
Silva M.L.E., De	Sec4ML: An approach to support Cybersecurity Data Publish	10.1109/EDOCW	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Despite the exponential growth of the World Wide Web since its creation,		
de França Mota I	Co-innovation in the clothes industry: Aggregating the customer's vision from o		https://www.scopus.com/inw	This study aims to create an algorithm to processes open data. The top e		
García-García J.	Online graphical visualisation tools for government open bud	10.3989/REDC.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The dissemination of public information by governments and administrati		
Correa A.S., Mel	A deep search method to survey data portals in the whole we	10.1016/j.giq.202	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The emergence of standardized open data software platforms has provid		
Rama Charan D.	Convolutional neural network based water resource monitorin	10.1109/ICCES4	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Perception of surface water is a utilitarian necessity for contemplating na		

Authors	Title	DOI	Link	Abstract	Relevant title?	Relevant abstract?
Zeleti F.A., Ojo A	Open data capability architecture - An interpretive structural modeling approach		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Despite of increasing availability of open data as a vital organizational re		
Dymora P., Mazu	Analysis of selected characteristics of open data inception portals in the contex		https://www.scopus.com/inw	In this study, we focus on Open Government Data, which is the sphere of		
van Loenen B., M	SPIDER: Open spatial data infrastructure education network		https://www.scopus.com/inw	In this 2 hour workshop the experiences of the geographic data domain v		
Wisnubhadra I., I	Open Spatiotemporal Data Warehouse for Agriculture Product	10.22266/ijies20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Business Intelligence (BI) technology with Extract, Transform, and Loadir		
Raad H., Robich	The pleiotropic effects of Innexin genes expressed in Drosop	10.1002/jnr.2448	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The neuroanatomy of Drosophila wing chemosensilla and the analysis of		
Mehdiabadi S.P.,	Explicit jet veto as a tool to purify the underlying event in the	10.1088/1361-64	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The underlying event (UE) is an important part of high-energy collision ev		
Zhai J., Liang Y.,	Research on semantic aggregation of shipping digital resourc	10.1109/ICSSSM	https://www.scopus.com/inw	With the advent of the era of big data, governments of all countries have		
Kim K., Lee K.	Towards ingestion processes of kompsat data in open data c	10.1109/IGARSS	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open Data Cube (ODC) is an open source platform that allows analysis e		
William East E., I	Analysis of life-cycle information exchange		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Although it is well known that construction project stakeholders pay for w		
Klímek J.	Reflections on: DCAT-AP representation of Czech national open data catalog e		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open data is now a heavily discussed topic around the world and in the E		
De Oliveira D.G.,	Evaluation of the Social Security's Open Data [Avaliação dos	10.22347/2175-2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The objective of this study was to evaluate whether the open data, made		
da Costa G.R., S	Health information systems applied to maternity hospitals: A s	10.1007/978-981	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The computerized medical record systems have been applied to enable t		
Mattern H., Köniç	Efficient management of design options for early BIM		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Investigating different design options constitutes an iterative process in th		
Sandoval-Almaz	The use of MOOCS in the open government virtual education	10.1145/3209281	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open government is a worldwide trend. Many countries started implemer		
Cook K.	Open data as public archaeology: The monumental archive p	10.23914/ap.v8i2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	The value of open data is transforming archaeological practice while also		
Kloda L.	Open data for evidence based practice	10.18438/ebli29	https://www.scopus.com/inw	[No abstract available]		
Sylvan E.	Data literacy as storytelling practice in the open data/open minds project		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Open Data/Open Minds is a series of educational initiatives that engage		
Wan J., Li L., Wa	An approach of entity alignment based on semantic features	10.1109/ICSS.2	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Entity alignment is to link 'equivalent' entities that denote the same objec		
Murillo L.F.R.	New expert eyes over fukushima: Open source responses to	10.1353/anq.201	https://www.scopus.com/inw	In this article, I explore the responses of the Open Source community to		
Navrotsky M., Zl	Scientific portal of university department-shaping research area of users throug		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Nowadays open access to scientific data in addition to obtaining informat		
Enríquez J.G., L	Entity identification problem in Big and Open Data	10.5220/0005470	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Big and Open Data provide great opportunities to businesses to enhance		
Arres B., Kabach	An original approach for processing public open data with Ma	10.1109/AICCSA	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Nowadays, many governments and states are involved in an opening str		
Koide S., Kato F.	An LOD practice lessons learned from open data METI		https://www.scopus.com/inw	The Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry of Japan has launched the		
Tian L., Zhang W	MeDetect: Domain entity annotation in biomedical references using linked open		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Recently, with the ever-growing use of textual medicine records, annotati		
Weyl J., Lenfers	Large-scale traffic simulation for smart city planning with mars		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Understanding individual mobility in larger cities is an important success		
Gaignard A., Ska	From scientific workflow patterns to 5-star linked open data		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Scientific Workflow management systems have been largely adopted by		
Kain M., Bodin M	Small Animal Shanoir (SAS) A Cloud-Based Solution for Man	10.3389/fninf.202	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Clinical multicenter imaging studies are frequent and rely on a wide rang		
De Vocht L., Dim	A visual exploration workflow as enabler for the exploitation of linked open data		https://www.scopus.com/inw	Semantically annotating and interlinking Open Data results in Linked Ope		
Artus M., Alabas	A BIM Based Framework for Damage Segmentation, Modelir	10.3390/app1206	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Paper-based data acquisition and manual transfer between incompatible		
Poirier O., De Ca	Modelling forest degradation and risk of disease outbreaks in	10.21037/jphe-20	https://www.scopus.com/inw	Background: Epidemiologists have testified for a rise of emerging infectio		